

LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF METHODS THAT INCREASE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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Annotation: It is believed that the communicative language teaching approach is one of the most effective methods to keep away from the weaknesses of the traditional English teaching method in developing students' communicative ability. Using games, which is communicative in essence, are often considered effective in developing students' communicative ability.

Keywords: communicative ability, games, suggestions, method, technology, language, speaking.

INTRODUCTION

Sometimes it is easy to get a new method like the communicative language teaching approach heard but difficult to get it accepted, understood and applied to practical classroom teaching in the end. Therefore, it is not out of date to discuss the techniques of applying the communicative language teaching approach to classroom teaching. In this paper, the author, on the basis of pointing out the disadvantages of the traditional teaching method, discusses and explores one way to teach students effectively – using games in the English class, which is often considered as one of the best way to get the students involved in the classroom activities in which their communicative ability is practised and improved. Language games, as one of the most valuable and effective techniques in English language teaching, have been used for a long time by many western teachers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There are many good ideas about English teaching. Among these, using games in the English class is the one which is most easily accepted by students and

which is also a very useful and helpful aspect of communicative method. As is known to everyone, game is an activity providing entertainment or amusement; it's a competitive activity or sport in which players contend with each other according to a set of rules. "A game is an activity carried out by co-operating or competing decision-makers, seeking to achieve, within a set of rules, their objectives" (Rixon 2011). A game is an activity that both the teacher and students enjoy doing. It is student-centered and as appealing as playing in the playground.

Games are communicative in essence, and so using game in English teaching and learning can well realize the fundamental idea of the communicative language teaching approach. Using games is a good way to improve students' various skills, as Wright, Betteridge and Buckby (2006) say, "Games can be found to give practice in all the skills, in all the stages of the teaching and learning and for many types of communication".

As stated above, the main purpose of using games in English classes is to practise students' different skills, especially their communicative ability. Here, eight types of games from published sources are identified, discussed and explored [1,2,3].

A. *Guessing Games*

The basic role of guessing games is very simple: one person knows something that another one wants to find out. The thing to be guessed can differ greatly from game to game. It can be a word, an object, an activity or many other things. Guessing games are useful in helping students practise logical thinking and asking questions. 3-item story is one example of a guessing game. One person in a group knows the story in which there are three items given to the other members of the group. *Picture Games*

Picture games include several types:

Comparing and contrasting pictures; Considering differences or similarities;
Considering possible relationships between pictures, such as narrative sequence;

Describing key features so that someone else may identify them or represent

them in a similar way; Making a story according to the given picture.

Most of these picture games involve the learners in the relatively free use of all the language at their command and at the same time give them the opportunity to practise their speaking and listening.

B. *Sound Games*

Sound effects can create in the listeners' mind an impression of people, places and actions. There is a demand for the listener to contribute through the imagination. This inevitably leads to individual interpretations which mean that the listeners can exchange their points of view and express opinions and ideas. This kind of games can stimulate students' imagination and thinking, and offer them a chance to practise their listening and speaking. Students can make guess at the object described by sound, or make dialogue or a story.

C. *Mime*

Mimes can be done in pairs, groups or even by the whole class. One side has to perform the mimes for the other side so that the answer can be found. It can be an object, action or person. So miming activities are valuable language-learning situations. Guessing something is linked with the real desire to find out and thus is a true communication situation. Miming trains the students' skill of observation and improvisation. It emphasizes the importance of gesture and facial expression in communication. *Fact-finding Games*

This mainly deals with general knowledge and is a very practical exercise. Everyday, there is something important happening, so the students can be asked what happened on a day in history. It may be a historical accident, a birthday of a famous person, or something strange or marvelous. Then further details can be asked. The students can discuss in pairs or groups in order to find much more information.

D. *Debates*

In this activity, a topic is given and two sides are set up, one supporting the idea and the other opposing it. Then they argue giving their evidence. The aim of

this activity is to get the students to talk and stimulate their interest and competitive spirit. Such activities make the students think about their values and priorities. There is no doubt that this activity will improve students` conversation and eloquence.

E. Role Plays

Role plays often consist of short scenes, which can be realistic or pure fantasy. Role plays may be enacted around everyday situations as well as around topical problems. One easily-obtained role play is from the text, which may be actual role play material.

CONCLUSION

From the above analysis, a conclusion can be drawn that teaching and learning English by means of language games is effective and efficient in improving students` communicative ability. While in the traditional method of teaching English, students sit still listening to teachers talking about English language and try their best to remember English words and grammatical rules by rote memory, in the communicative language teaching approach they are actively involved in playing games which in turn can arouse and maintain their interest in learning, promote their motivation of study, and at the same time get lots of opportunities to have their basic skills of listening and speaking practiced.

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